

Psychological Issues and Challenges of Hotel as Quarantine Facility: Policy and Guidelines

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Abstract

The COVID-19 global health crisis has spatial implications in terms of social isolation in order to control the virus's spread. Due to a lack of government facilities, more hotels are now serving as quarantine facilities. The study's main objectives are to recommend issues and challenges parameters of the hotels as quarantine facilities as guides to develop policies and guidelines, to comprehend and recognize issues and challenges parameters of the hotels as quarantine facilities under the New Normal, and to ascertain significant relationship in respondents' perspective when considering various variables. Hospitality industries interested in policy and guidelines should first consider the check-in and check-out procedures, room cleaning procedures, food preparation, and services and develop new policies and guidelines or develop existing policies and guidelines that can result in positive performance based on their identified needs, policy, and resources. The Check-in and Check-out Procedures are the recent issues and challenges in a hotel as a quarantine facility. Guests nowadays expect this factor to be the primary consideration when selecting with quarantine facility, including but limited to having functional front office services, such as the pre-arrival information about the hotel should be given prior to check-in, guests must have the option of choosing a preferred room with complete facilities and amenities, are allowed to use other hotel services and facilities such as recreational facilities, understand the room rate and other charges, are regularly monitored by a BOQ, DOH, or other government representatives and provide clearance from both the hotel and BOQ prior to check out. The study's findings are limited in their generalizability due to the fact that it was done at only in hotels in three cities located in Metro Manila, resulting in a small sample size and inadequate statistical analysis.

Keywords: hotel quarantine, best practices, policy, issues and challenges, health protocol

1. Introduction

Tourism plays an important role in any country around the world. It brings revenue to its country and creates jobs. In the Philippines, we boast of rich natural beauty in its spectacular beaches, sunny weather, hospitable people, and rich bio-diversity. More than that, the Philippines is known for its unique and complex culture, as exemplified by its people, cuisines, and, lifestyle, which attracts many people to visit the country. Without a doubt, the Tourism Industry is one of the sectors that has been most devastated by the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the World Tourism Organization, the closure of borders, airports, and hotels, as well as restrictions on mass gatherings, land travel, and related services, has put 100 to 120 million jobs at harm around the world. In the Philippines, the government closed all airports in March 2020 as part of the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ), which began on March 16, 2020. The tourism industry has already begun to feel the effects of the pandemic on its performance. Travel restrictions and measures in other countries began in January of the same year, affecting international visitor arrivals in the Philippines. Travelers, on the other hand, restricted their travel due to worries about acquiring COVID-19. According to the Department of Tourism, international tourist arrivals declined to 36% or PHP 85 billion in the first quarter compared to the same period last year. (PWC, 2020). There are more than thirteen (13) Tourism Sectors, and one of those is the Hotel. A hotel is a definition-stop-shop entity, this means they are not only providing accommodation but also other services such as food and beverages, spa, gym, travel and tours, airfare, transportation, special events, etc. The hotel has different types depending on their services and facilities, from luxurious to economical. Prices also depend on the locations, facilities, and services. Hotel operators/chain has the prerogative to be accredited by the Department of Tourism (DOT). DOT uses a star system to rate hotels according to their services, personnel, facilities, and, processes, from 1 star is the lowest which is equivalent to the economy, and 5 Stars to the highest corresponding to Deluxe, certification validity is

good for five (5) years. (Roldan, A, 2014). On the proposal of DOT, the director of DOT's Office of Tourism Standards and Regulations, planned to adopt the international star system headed by international assessors from the UK, Canada, and Australia and a pool of local third-party auditors. To be used for our country which has around 700 hotels and resorts. The former rating system, which the DOT had been using since the 1990s, has been replaced by the new star rating system for hotels and resorts. The former rating system, which the DOT had been using since the 1990s, has been replaced by the new star rating system for hotels and resorts. Hotels were given ratings of Economy, Standard, First-Class, and Deluxe under the old system, and resorts received ratings of A, AA, and AAA. (Calleja, 2022). One of the popular 5-star hotels in the country was closed during the time of the pandemic. Shangri-La Hotel chain in the Philippines has six (6) that include Makati Shangri-La Hotel which is located in the Main Business District and was closed last February 1, 2021. The hotel first opened its doors in 1993 and has since been recognized as a landmark of Makati City. As hotel operator reorganizes their workforce and operations in Southeast Asian nation due to "continued business levels. According to the Shangri-La hotel chain, it will continue to vigilant monitor the developments and looks forward to re-opening the hotel when the business conditions have improved. Alegado and Yap, (Bloomberg, 2021). Marco Polo in Davao was also closed last May 2020, (Rappler.com) According to Business World, 2020, an article entitled, Hotels turn to quarantine business to survive the coronavirus pandemic. Last March 2020, Robinsons Hotels was one of the first to take this quarantine business and about 90% of them. They operated the reasonably priced Go Hotel brand and the 3-star Summit Hotels brand aside from other hotel properties such as the Dusit Thani Hotel in Cebu, otherwise, they will close. On Sept 29, 2020, it was followed by The Golden Phoenix Hotel in Pasay City to survive the crisis, then lastly, Chroma Hospitality's Quest Hotel in Tagaytay. More than 300 local hotels were included in the programs used as quarantine facilities. The Bureau of Quarantine (BOQ) said on its website in August. Consequently, hotels also catered to BPO employees who due to the lockdown and unavailability of public transport lived very close to their work. While Robinsons converted some of its rooms into long-term accommodations and office spaces, the Crimson Manila Hotel in Muntinlupa City catered to BPO employees and other workers. Hotels are required by health and safety regulations to provide digital check-ins and contactless services.

The Bureau of Quarantine (BOQ) provides a list of hotels to serve as quarantine facilities. As of June 2020. There were one hundred sixteen (116) hotels as quarantine facilities suitable for mandatory quarantine, likewise, one hundred twelve (112) hotels as quarantine facilities were approved for stringent quarantine. BOQ continues to assess the hotels as quarantine facilities to date with DOT-accredited quarantine facilities as of July 8, 2022. Today there are about one-hundred seventy-three (173) hotels as quarantine facilities suitable for mandatory quarantine, one-hundred fifty-nine (159) hotels as quarantine facilities were approved for stringent quarantine, and hotels as quarantine facilities suitable only for mandatory quarantine on signing seafarers for about twenty (20). These hotels located in NCR vary from 5 stars to 1 star as quarantine facilities are located in NCR.

Complaints about the hotel as a quarantine facility were reported by one of the OFWs who work for a cruise ship. At first, he appreciated the presence of the DOH personnel at the airport who assisted them in checking their medical status. The group was sent to one of the hotels in Quezon City. When they got to their assigned guestroom, they were shocked at the situation. The room was dirty and not ready for guests. One of the groups posted pictures of their rooms on their Twitter account, showing the presence of cockroaches, waste on top of the air condition, wrinkled not fresh, and dirty bedsheets, a dirty door rug, a dirty and stained toilet bowl, and untidy floors. Aside from the disgusting guestroom, he also mentioned and commented on the guidelines given by the manning agency from DOH and BOQ that say, "They are not allowed to post anything on social media nor grant media interviews, otherwise their phones will be confiscated." (ABS CBN, 2021) There was an incident that happened last December 22, 2021, when a female Filipino returned from the United States and checked in to Berjaya Hotel (quarantine facility) in Makati, where at the same night, the patient guest was fetched by her father and attended the so-called party with their family. Then came back to the hotel on the 25th of December, 2021. The guest patient tested positive last December 26 and was pulled from their current hotel facility and transferred to an isolation facility in Metro Manila. The PNP filed cases against returning overseas Filipino who breached quarantine protocols together with their family and the hotel management. Furthermore, the CIDG cannot find sufficient evidence" to charge any of the individuals in the company of Chua the night after she broke quarantine. (Philstar, 2022).

These concerns were from OFWs who work in Canada. According to them, a government representative directed them to the hotel in Makati City as their quarantine facility. They had no complaints about the facilities and services of the hotel. Their concern was that their bill had reached P50,000 because the hotel provides only three (3) meals a day, and the hotel does not allow food delivery, so they ordered room service because they were waiting for DOH to do the COVID swab test so that they could go home. (ABS CBN, 2022)

Filipino passengers from South Korea who had already booked their hotel accommodations prior to their arrival were canceled due to the advice of government personnel from the airport. According to Lalu, Gabriel of inquirer.net (De, 2020), they were shuttled to one hotel in Tagaytay City, where they will spend their mandatory quarantine. Unfortunately, the passengers were so disappointed that they complained. They found out that the hotel rooms assigned to them were dirty and stench. They opted to stay outside of the hotel. They have seen the hotel room bathrooms, bowls and beds were untidy, with low to no water flow, and with a bad smell. They also mentioned that our government promised to provide the two with hotels to choose from and payment would be taken care of by our government which never happened. They felt that they are being hostage. They also thought they can only stay at the hotel for three (3) days, not 14 days, due to no concrete instructions given to them. Their total experience at the hotel as a quarantine facility was untidy and had a stench that made it unlivable.

This research will focus on issues and challenges of the hotel as a Quarantine Facility to provide the basis for policy and guidelines as well as preparedness to face the same event in our country. Numerous complaints arose last 2020 from our heroes, the OFWs, and Filipino migrants and their families who returned home during the pandemic. As the foundation for guidelines or policies, this research will provide concrete guidelines or policies on how to resolve the issues and challenges of the hotel as a quarantine facility.

I. Purpose and objective of the study

Hotels have been repurposed as quarantine centers to help prevent the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, which is still damaging the world. However, this has created a number of concerns and challenges. To begin, hotels must ensure that they have the necessary facilities and resources to handle quarantined individuals, such as enough medical and cleaning staff, personal protective equipment, and enough ventilation systems. Second, appropriate methods for managing quarantined individuals, such as check-in and check-out procedures, meal preparations, and medical care, are required. Furthermore, in terms of room allocation and cleaning schedules, hotels must balance the needs of quarantined individuals with those of their normal customers. To solve these issues, hotels must create clear policies and standards that promote safety and satisfaction for both patient-guest and hotel staff.

The objective of the study is to present a guideline or policy by determining the issues and challenges of a hotel as a quarantine facility.

1. To identify the issues and challenges of hotels as quarantine facilities that can be used to develop policies and guidelines.
2. The implementation of hotel best practices that affect guest satisfaction.
3. Is there a significant relationship between the issues and challenges of hotel services and practices implementation that affect guest satisfaction?

2. Literature Review

Arrival and Quarantine procedures for Filipino and Foreign Nationals

Philippine Airlines (PAL), our flag carrier provides also guidelines on their website with regard to the passengers that need to undergo facility-based quarantine. The guidelines stated that those passengers are required to go through facility-based quarantine, need to check in at their hotel, and wait for scheduled swab tests depending scheduled to be sent through their email addresses within 24-48 hours. Thus facility-based quarantine is no longer required for fully vaccinated passengers. As for payment PAL also included in their announcement that for OFWs, their accommodation and food during their stay will be shouldered by the Philippine government but for non-

OFWs, their accommodation and food during their stay will be at their own expense. They also mentioned in compliance with Philippine regulations, delivery of outside food to their hotel is not allowed. As for non-OFWs and foreign nationals who are required to undergo facility-based quarantine, must ensure to have a confirmed booking (with transportation arrangements) at a hotel that must be accredited by Tourism and Health Agencies. Passengers arriving before hotel standard check-in times are encouraged to book an additional night to ensure room availability. They must stay at their booked hotel for their scheduled test and until the tenth day of your quarantine stays after the negative test result is sent. PAL also provided a list of DOH-inspected hotels in Clark as a quarantine facility. (philippineairlines.com, 2021).

Figure 1. Procedure of the “hotel quarantine voyage” as illustrated by the authors.

The adaptation of hotels as quarantine facilities started when the hotels or accommodation establishments were prohibited by the government from accepting guests or tourists during the pandemic to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 virus. Since nobody prepared for this COVID-19 pandemic, policies and guidelines on quarantine keep changing. Despite the destructive effects of COVID-19 on the hospitality industry and the lack of state quarantine institutions and facilities, the concept of converting hotels into quarantine facilities might be seen as a responsive response.

Safety precautions for the mandatory and stringent quarantine adhere to anti-epidemic and disinfection regulations and are supported by updated hotel service evaluations. For a period of 14 days, guests using the hotel as a quarantine facility during an isolation period are not allowed to leave their allotted rooms. They are not permitted access to public areas or hotel amenities like the spa, gym, pool, spa, bar and, gym is not allowed available to them.

Quarantine Facilities Interim guidance

An international guideline for quarantine facilities

was issued called *Interim guidance* developed by a review of WHO and UNWTO guidance documents and internal consultation at WHO, UNWTO, and UNICEF last August 25, 2020, and was published last March 31, 2020. It was designed to cover hotels and other accommodation facilities of all sizes. *Interim guidance* involves all types of hotels or accommodations facilities. It focuses on the (1) welfare of both guest and hotel staff, (2) to communicate with the local government when the guest is found infected, (3) contact tracing (4) logbook of actions, to record the suspected/confirmed case (5) providing guidelines to the staff on how they should communicate to guests and other stakeholders can ensure privacy and consistency. (6) practice social distancing (7) proper ventilation of the room (8) guidance for hygiene and food safety (9) guests are allowed to go to the restaurant or dining area and reminded when entering and leaving the restaurant, breakfast, or dining room to clean their hands using alcohol-based hand rub, preferably located at the entrances and exits of those facilities. (10) Buffets are not recommended and should not be offered. (11) Gym, beach, swimming pool, spa, sauna, and steam bath facilities can be used with restrictions, in accordance with relevant national guidelines, and (12) housekeeping services, cleaning, and disinfection of public areas only. On the contrary, hotel guests should be well taken care of in terms of their needs while having the mandatory quarantine. There should be clear guidelines from the hotel as a quarantine facility, the guestrooms should be adequately prepared for the well-being needs of guests isolated for 14 days.

Hotellers preferred hotels nowadays as quarantine rather than staycation facilities as their source of income.

One of the hotels in Metro Manila that had a chance

to be a quarantined hotel. Their marketing and sales director stated that *“a little profit is better than no profit at all,”* They prefer to remain in a quarantine facility instead of applying to shift into a staycation hotel. According to them returning migrant Filipinos appear to be more dependable sources of income than tourists staying in hotels. Where guests, remain in quarantine longer than typical travelers who typically stay just only for a night. (BW, 2020)

Safe and Sound with DOT Accredited Hotels

Accreditation is not mandatory for all providers in the tourism industry. Since the cost starts from half a million for regular and premium for one million. The main objective of DOT accreditation is to professionalize and standardize the quality of services provided by tourism establishments such as hotel accommodations, ticketing, packaged tours, and transportation. The accreditation assists the DOT in monitoring each travel and tourism establishment's compliance with the industry's standards. At the same time, consumers are protected from untrustworthy or even fly-by-night operations and poor service. (Ylagan, 2019)

Hoteliers' Responsibility to their Patient-Guest

The reliability and responsiveness of hotel staff members were shown to be the most important aspects of guests' opinions of the services they experienced in a quarantined hotel. In addition to encouraging guests to stay again, hotel managers of premises that are under quarantine should carefully assess the services they offer. (Wang et.al, 2021)

The announcement for concrete protocols for both arriving international and returning Filipino passengers to the Philippines was posted by the Philippine airline (PAL) last June 26, 2022. According to the advisory, *“International passengers must follow the arrival procedures of their PH port of entry mandated by PAL and the Philippine Government. Unvaccinated, partially vaccinated, and passengers whose vaccination status cannot be verified shall be required to complete a facility-based quarantine at the first port of entry into the Philippines, regardless of the onward domestic destination. Ensure to check your first PH arrival airport prior to booking the facility”*. Philippine Embassy from other countries has different protocols such as Phnom Penh, Cambodia, Singapore, and Norway. See below for your reference.

International passengers must follow the arrival procedures of their PH port of entry mandated by PAL and the Philippine Government

Public advisory updated testing and quarantine protocols for arriving international passengers to the Philippines, Embassy of the Philippines Phnom Penh, Cambodia

Guidelines For Travel to The Philippines (Non-OFWs and Foreign Nationals), The Embassy of The Philippines, Singapore

Dincer and Ozgur,(2021) explained that when a tourist entering Australia is required to go through a so-called " quarantine journey," which is authorized and regulated by each state with minor changes, due to legally mandated regulations. Prior to their arrival, arriving guests are told of the quarantine procedure that will be used to protect them. Law enforcers are typically in charge of transportation between airports and hotels, and passengers are directed to designated buses that operate at a maximum of half capacity. After checking in, guests are briefly led in small groups to the hotel lobby before being accompanied to their rooms. Because of this, the 14-day quarantine stay is restricted to hotel rooms due to legal constraints. The guests were advised about what to expect during their stay, the Australian government distributed the brochure "Getting Ready for Quarantine." The document stated that hotels will offer three meals every day, with variations amongst facilities. The guests may expect basic Wi-Fi, a telephone, and a television in addition; nevertheless, they would be responsible for paying for washing services. The rooms wouldn't be cleaned throughout their stay due to COVID-19 regulations. Smoking wasn't permitted in the rooms, and people quarantined couldn't smoke either. The opening page of the document provided the visitors with stating that "quarantining in a hotel will be different from your typical experience of staying in a hotel," and that it might be impossible.

Fida et al. (2020) specified a few aspects that influence customer satisfaction. These include physical facilities, service timelines, hotel staff proper decorum, availability of equipment needed, communication techniques, and responses to customer complaints. They also include efficiency, data accuracy, service consistency, problem resolution situations, attention to detail, staff flexibility, and a staff attitude toward providing customer support. Staff behavior, customer security, courtesy, staff competence, personalized customer attention, service availability in all durations, and understanding of guest-specific preferences.

When it comes to guest satisfaction, cleanliness matters. All problems experienced by guests' unclean rooms have the greatest negative impact on satisfaction. A recent study conducted by different hotel booking sites found that more than 60% of hotel guests read reviews before booking the accommodation and 71% of guests expect "above average" cleanliness ratings when choosing a hotel. (HN, 2018)

3. Methodology

The data collected for this research is based on both guests (participants) and hotel employees' hotel quarantine experiences during the required mandatory quarantine. The study also used the quantitative method of research utilizing a structured survey questionnaire for data gathering. Statistical treatment of data to be used are frequency, percentage, weighted mean, Likert scale, and chi-square. The researchers used purposive sampling. The primary respondents of the study are an estimated 100 employees from hotels located in Metro Manila, Philippines. While secondary respondents are 100 those 18 years old and above who spent the required number of days in quarantine in, a specified hotel given by the DOH. The researchers shall make use of an electronic questionnaire and be sent to their FB messenger, IG, IMO, Viber, WhatsApp, email addresses, and other social media platforms. Ethical considerations were also observed and practiced. The researchers shall strictly follow Republic Act No. 10173, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act on the part of the respondents and to the subject of our study. The name of hotels, employees, and guests are purely confidential.

4. Result And Discussion

Result of Objective No. 1: Issues and challenges encountered by the guest at the hotel as quarantine facility.

A. The issues and challenges the guest encountered at the hotel as a quarantine facility during check-in and check-out procedures. Based on the survey results, it seems that most of the respondents were extremely satisfied with the clearance provided by both the hotel and BOQ prior to checkout, which is great news. However, there were some areas of concern. Participants reported being highly satisfied with the limited use of hotel services and facilities, such as recreational facilities, with a weighted mean of 3.21. This could suggest that participants felt restricted in their ability to enjoy certain amenities during their stay. In addition, some participants reported feeling neglected in terms of regular monitoring by the BOQ, DOH, or other government representatives on their quarantine status. This is important because it ensures that individuals are receiving the necessary care and attention while in quarantine. Interestingly, these findings contradict the WHO interim Guidance from 2020, which suggests that facilities such as gyms, beaches, and swimming pools can be used with restrictions in accordance with national guidelines. It's important to take these findings into consideration when developing quarantine policies and procedures to ensure the safety and satisfaction of all individuals in quarantine.

B. Challenges encountered by the guests at the hotel as a quarantine facility in terms of room cleaning procedures. According to the survey results, it seems that respondents were highly satisfied with the housekeeping services provided during their stay. They appreciated being informed about the makeup room schedule, where room attendants replenish room amenities and towels every day, with a weighted mean of 3.21. This suggests that participants were not satisfied with the standard of cleaning and disinfection of their bathroom and bowl. It's important to recognize the hard work of housekeeping personnel or room attendants and their role in ensuring a comfortable and clean stay for guests. However, this finding highlights the need for continued monitoring and provide necessary training to maintain a high standard of cleanliness and disinfection in all areas of the room. By doing so, we can ensure that guests feel safe and comfortable during their stay. Unfortunately, there was a specific incident in Tagaytay City where Filipino passengers from South Korea had a negative experience during their quarantine stay at a hotel. They were disappointed and had to file complaints because they discovered that their hotel rooms were dirty and had an unpleasant odor. They even opted to stay outside of the hotel because of the untidiness they observed in the bathroom, bowl, and beds, with low to no water flow. This made their overall experience in the hotel as a quarantine facility unlivable. It's important to address situations like these and ensure that hotels are achieving the necessary standards for cleanliness and comfort, especially during these challenging times (Lalu, 2020)

C. Facility experience in terms of Food Preparation and Services. The survey results revealed that there may be some issues in the food and beverage department of the hotel. It seems that the importance of freshness and the right temperature in the food and drinks served may not be observed consistently. Some guests reported receiving limited or incomplete meals during their stay. This finding is particularly concerning because, under Philippine regulations, guests under quarantine are not allowed to purchase food from outside sources, whether through personal means or online delivery. This means that they are reliant on the hotel's room service to fulfill their hunger. In situations like these, suggestive selling through room service can be a helpful approach to ensure that guests are getting the most out of their meals. It's important for hotels to prioritize the quality and healthy food being served to ensure the satisfaction and well-being of guests during their quarantine stay. Customer satisfaction is dependent on a business's efforts to provide high-quality services (Sharma & Srivasta, 2018).

Result Objective No. 2: Based on the survey results, it can be concluded that implementing health protocols has a significant impact on guest satisfaction in quarantine facilities, with a weighted mean of 3.60 and a verbal interpretation of "strongly agree." This finding emphasizes the importance of prioritizing the health and safety of guests, especially during a pandemic. However, communication received the lowest weighted mean of 3.27 with a verbal interpretation of "strongly agree." This implies that there is room for improvement in terms of how hotels communicate with their guests during their quarantine stay. It is crucial for hotels to provide clear and timely information to their guests, especially on matters related to health protocols, meals, and housekeeping services. According to the World Health Organization Interim Guidance, 2020, hotels used as quarantine facilities should prioritize health and safety measures such as frequent cleaning and disinfection, availability of hand hygiene facilities, and proper waste management (WHO, 2020). Clear and effective communication is also essential in ensuring that guests understand and comply with these protocols. Therefore, hotels used as quarantine facilities should prioritize the implementation of health protocols and improve communication with their guests. This will not only improve guest satisfaction but also ensure the safety and well-being of everyone in the facility (Lalu, 2020).

5. Hypothesis Testing

The issues and challenges encountered by the guests at the hotel as a quarantine facility and the implementation of hotel best practices that affect guest satisfaction are positively correlated with $r(17) = .91, p < .00001$. The result is significant at $p < .05$. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the issues and challenges of hotel services and best practices implementation that affects guest satisfaction.

Fida et al. (2020) suggest that when it comes to customer satisfaction in hotels, it's best to focus on a few key aspects. These include things like the physical facilities, making sure they are clean and comfortable, and that any equipment or amenities needed by guests are readily available. It's also important for hotel staff to have proper decorum and communication techniques, as well as be responsive to customer complaints. Other factors that can impact guest satisfaction include the efficiency and accuracy of hotel services, consistent problem resolution, attention to detail, and staff flexibility and attitude toward customer support. It's also important for hotel staff to prioritize customer security, courtesy, competence, and personalized attention. Finally, ensuring that hotel services are available at all times and understanding guest-specific preferences can go a long way in improving overall guest satisfaction.

Wang et al. (2021) pointed out that guests' opinions of the services they experienced in a quarantined hotel were strongly influenced by the reliability and responsiveness of hotel staff members. These findings emphasize the critical role of hotel staff in providing a positive experience for guests, especially during these challenging times. To encourage guests to return, hotel managers of quarantine facilities should prioritize assessing and improving the services they offer, including staff training and development, to ensure that their guests feel safe, comfortable, and well-cared for throughout their stay.

In a study conducted by Teng et al. (2021), they proposed the idea of a "corporate quarantine hotel" as a social responsibility towards public health and its impact on stakeholders and hotel staff. This emphasizes the need for hotels to play an active role in promoting public health, especially during a pandemic. Meanwhile, Choi and Choi's qualitative study focused on the staff and stakeholders of quarantine hotels in South Korea. They interviewed

hotel staff and gathered insights on their experiences working in a quarantine facility. Their findings were consistent with the research conducted by Goh and Baums, emphasizing the importance of prioritizing staff well-being and safety in quarantine hotels. These studies highlight the significance of considering both the guests and the hotel staff in implementing best practices for quarantine hotels.

6. Conclusion

Analysis of the result simply means that the hotel's function as a place for vacation or staycation is different when functioning as a quarantine facility. The conversion of hotels to provide patient guests (OFWs, Filipino immigrants, and international passengers) during mandatory or stringent quarantine was a quick response to COVID-19-related spatial demands. The rooms could not be properly prepared in such a short period of time for the well-being of people who had been isolated for 14 days. Likewise, there were no definite and clear instructions from the government offices in charge of the COVID-19 response of guests from pre-arrival to the standard number of days to a mandatory or stringent quarantine period at the hotel as a quarantine facility.

7. Recommendation

The hotel's goal is to ensure that guests have 100% satisfaction throughout their stay, starting from the reservation process, registration, room and rate assignment, and even providing various services such as food and beverage, housekeeping, banquet and catering, transportation, business center, travel and tours, foreign exchange, souvenirs, and recreational services. The top priority of the housekeeping department is to maintain cleanliness in the guest rooms and public areas, and they have round-the-clock personnel to monitor it. Guests can even enjoy personalized assistance from butlers, which is a service typically offered by 5-star hotels. With the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic still present in our community, it is crucial to prioritize health and safety measures. The Department of Health advises that we should get vaccinated and strictly follow the minimum health protocols to prevent getting infected again.

To address the growing concerns about future epidemics, it is crucial for the government to establish a clear and comprehensive protocol for our OFWs, Filipino returning immigrants, and international tourists when it comes to quarantine facilities. This will make it easier for them to understand and follow the guidelines for a safe and healthy quarantine experience. Furthermore, hotels that will be used as quarantine facilities should be accredited by the Department of Tourism (DOT) to ensure that guests receive quality service and enjoy their stay. By working together and implementing these measures, we can ensure the safety and well-being of everyone in our communities. DOT accreditation serves as a way to ensure that tourism establishments, such as hotels, offer high-quality services to their customers. This program aims to standardize the quality of services provided by tourism establishments, including hotel accommodations, transportation, ticketing, and packaged tours. It helps the DOT monitor the compliance of each tourism establishment with the industry's standards. Through this, customers are protected from fraudulent or unreliable operations that may provide poor service. This also helps to ensure that tourists have a safe and enjoyable experience during their stay in the Philippines.

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